

RI4C2
Research & Innovation
For Cities & Citizens

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101035803

EC2U Makeathon - “Reinvent the Future”

Report

DELIVERABLE 5.7
MONTH 34

D5.7 EC2U Makeathon

Table of contents

I. Describing the Makeathon	4
A. Rationale	4
B. Summary with key figures	6
C. Stakeholders involved.....	7
II. Preparation.....	9
A. Organisation.....	9
B. Communication and visibility.....	10
III. Trainings	13
IV. The Makeathon events	14
A. Overview.....	14
B. Coimbra	16
C. Iași.....	19
D. Jena.....	20
E. Pavia.....	23
F. Poitiers.....	26
G. Salamanca	28
H. Turku.....	28
I. Virtual track.....	30
V. Follow-up activities	33
VI. Evaluation	34
A. Quantitative feedback	34
B. Quotes from participants.....	35
C. Quotes from challenge-givers and partners	39
VII. Lessons learned.....	41

VIII. Conclusion	42
IX. Annexes	43
A. Annex A: EC2U Makeathon form (registration form with challenges offered)	43
B. Annex B : Makeathon Handbook	66

I. Describing the Makeathon

A. Rationale

The EC2U Makeathon of the RI4C2 project was an impactful event that brought together students, professionals, and stakeholders from across Europe to collaboratively “re-invent the future”. This report provides a comprehensive overview of the Makeathon, detailing its rationale, key statistics, organisational efforts, communication strategies, training sessions, individual Makeathon events in various cities including the developed solutions, follow-up activities, and evaluation.

Innovative event formats like hackathons or makeathons foster a culture of innovation and offer a space to co-create solutions. Together with an awareness to societal challenges and the bringing together of diverse stakeholders, those events create meaningful impact. These benefits are in line with the mission of the EC2U Alliance and the Pan-European Knowledge Ecosystem (PEKE) of the RI4C2 project.

With this objective in mind, a first joint EC2U Makeathon was organised inviting the whole EC2U community (students, staff, teachers, researchers, citizens, entrepreneurs, city representatives etc.) to reflect on specific challenges and bring innovative solutions.

The Makeathon was an effective format for empowering people and local institutions in identifying concrete local challenges that match the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (UNSDGs), and for bringing together different stakeholders such as students, researchers, and citizens as well as local institutions. The intention was to bring the global missions of each UNSDGs to the local level by tackling concrete challenges faced by local actors. Around these, participants from various disciplines and sectors formed teams and developed first solutions within a short but intense time span. This fostered empowerment, belonging and self-efficacy for the individuals.

The key elements of the Makeathon were:

- Tackling challenges related to four areas connected to the EC2U R&I Agenda and the UNSDGs: Wellbeing & Happiness, Diversity & Inclusion, Nature & Sustainability, Peace & Democracy.

- Collaboration within diverse teams within a short timeframe,
- Developing first steps of original solutions to the challenges.
- Additionally, showcasing achievements from across Europe helped to inspire more co-creation across various sectors and disciplines.

The RI4C2 project proposal was written in the context of the COVID-19 pandemic and envisioned the Makeathon as a merely virtual event. However, to increase the impact and to better embed RI4C2 in each city, the Management Committee jointly agreed on 18th of April, 2023 to implement it in a hybrid mode, with an event location in each EC2U city.

The Makeathon is a dynamic event that offers a creative learning experience while fostering collaboration and intercultural connections. Each EC2U/RI4C2 stakeholder could benefit from the event in their own way:

1. Students and Citizens: A Makeathon provides a platform for students and citizens to immerse themselves in hands-on activities. It not only encourages creative thinking and teamwork but also empowers participants to address meaningful challenges and work on innovative projects. Beyond these, it serves as a unique learning opportunity where students acquire new skills, exchange knowledge with like-minded peers from across Europe, and gain exposure to cutting-edge ideas and technologies. *Participants received certificates of participation, recognising their dedication.*

2. EC2U Community: The Makeathon plays a vital role in showcasing the innovative capacity of the EC2U Pan-European Knowledge Ecosystem. By bringing together stakeholders from diverse professional backgrounds, disciplines, and universities, this event fosters a collaborative environment that strengthens both local and European knowledge ecosystems. It encourages the sharing of knowledge and the creation of new ideas, strengthening the potential of the ecosystem.

3. Universities: Participating universities benefit significantly from the Makeathon. It provides an opportunity for these institutions to demonstrate their commitment to interdisciplinary collaboration, innovation, experimental learning, and creative problem-solving. Engagement of experts and industry professionals further enhances universities' partnerships with local companies and organisations, reinforcing their role as hubs for cutting-edge knowledge and practical solutions development.

4. Cities: The Makeathon attracts talented individuals from various fields, offering cities a unique opportunity to tap into a diverse pool of knowledge and skills. Beyond this, it nurtures sustainable awareness of local challenges and celebrates innovative solutions that directly benefit the community. The event not only fosters a culture of problem-solving but also strengthens the bond between cities and their inhabitants.

5. Companies: For companies, the Makeathon represents an opportunity to become (or show themselves as) enablers of innovation. They can provide guidance to participants, sharing their knowledge expertise. Additionally, the Makeathon serves as a platform for companies to connect with talented students, offering potential internships, bachelor's or master's thesis opportunities, and even potential job placements. Participating in the Makeathon enables companies to actively engage in the nurturing of the next generation of innovators while reinforcing their presence in the academic and professional landscape.

B. Summary with key figures

Track	Keywords of the challenges tackled	No. of challenges identified/offered	No. of challenges tackled	No. of participants
Coimbra	Isolation of rural populations and loneliness. Healthy eating habits and reduction of food waste. Prevention of school failure.	6	3	6
Iasi	Greener and quicker transportation. Increased well-being through transportation solutions. Stress and health management through better transportation.	4	1	4
Jena	Participatory digital education. Importance of trees in cities. Multifunctional community space. Big data for cities and citizens.	6	4	14
Pavia	Life-work balance. International students housing. Safe University campus. Sustainable cosmetics. Youth participation in EU elections.	5	5	16
Poitiers	Patient care in hospitals. Rain water and urban cool islands. Women's experience in public space. Promotion of physical activity.	8	4	11
Turku	Urban nature. Socialising areas. Equal education opportunities. Reducing loneliness.	4	4	15

Virtual track	Effective science communication. Socialising areas and activities.	4 ¹	2	6
Summary	Diverse challenges representing four areas: Wellbeing & Happiness, Diversity & Inclusion, Nature & Sustainability, Peace & Democracy.	37	23	72

The EC2U Makeathon was composed of seven individual event tracks across Europe: Coimbra, Iasi, Jena, Pavia, Poitiers, Turku and the virtual track. In total, more than 20 non-university actors supported the Makeathon as challenge-givers, mentors, and partners. In total, 37 challenges were collected from local stakeholders in four areas: Wellbeing & Happiness, Diversity & Inclusion, Nature & Sustainability, Peace & Democracy.

During the 24 hours of the event, all locations were connected for the Opening, two check-ins and the Grand Finale. Ultimately, 23 solutions to specific challenges were developed and presented by 23 teams, formed by around 70 successful participants. Local juries gave valuable feedback, awarded each team with an individual award category (e.g., “the most inclusive approach” or “the most visionary idea”). In addition, the seven local winning teams were awarded with a wooden star award and a “Ticket to Poitiers” (D1.8 Official Launch of the PEKE).

C. Stakeholders involved

The Makeathon was an opportunity to reach out to a multitude of local stakeholders, to connect actors and projects under specific mission areas, and to initiate and deepen relationships with non-academic stakeholders.

University services and projects: EC2U Think Tank Team; International Mobility unit University of Pavia; Green Office at University of Jena; Union of University Students Pavia; Fondation Poitiers Université; Lichtwerkstatt Makerspace; Entrepreneurial Hub Konttori; QG Sport Santé; SPVR Poitiers; Institute of Interdisciplinary Research of the University of Coimbra; EqualSteam Project; EC2U Coordination Team at the Johannes Kepler University Linz; ...

¹ In addition to 4 unique challenges, 5 were duplicates from local tracks on the wish of the challenge givers to offer it to local and virtual European teams.

Researchers and research units from the universities: Diego Alatorre, Researcher (Coimbra); Pâmela Aguiar, PhD Student and Gender@UC Project Manager; Ana Carvalho, Researcher (Coimbra); Bärbel Kracke, Professor of Educational Psychology (Jena); Bettina Böhm, Research Associate in Geoinformation Science (Jena); Department of Geography and Geology (Turku); Laurent Bosquet, Chaire Sport Santé and MOVE Research Lab (Poitiers); Marion Albouy, CHU Poitiers and EBI Lab (Poitiers); INVEST Research Flagship Centre (Turku); ...

Municipalities and city-related entities: City of Turku; Municipality of Jena; Municipality of Pavia; Info Jeunes Nouvelle Aquitaine - Europe Direct Poitiers Vienne / Deux-Sèvres; Néoloji Technopole Grand Poitiers; Grand Poitiers urban community; StadtLab Jena; ...

Companies and other entities, including non-profit associations and private actors: ELEVA Digital Development Agency; Civica Iasi; Volkshochschule (Community College) Jena; Iulius Group Iasi; Jena Digital network; JenaVersum network; ETICHUB company; association Le P'tit Prince; Iberdrola company; Polo Tecnologico; Instituto Pedro Nunes Coimbra; POP start-up incubator Poitiers; ...

II. Preparation

A. Organisation

In order to facilitate the organisation of the Makeathon in six different on-site locations and online, several documents were provided by the Work Package Leader:

- a handbook for internal use
- a communication plan and communication templates
- a script for the actual event

1. Handbook

The handbook (see Annex B.) detailed the objective as well as the expected outcome of the Makeathon. Furthermore, it gave instructions on the different roles and the way to find stakeholders and gather challenges, the general timeline and the first event organisation details.

At each location, people and institutions contributed in the following roles:

- **Participants:** Students, pupils, citizens, employees, entrepreneurs, and others who actively engaged in the Makeathon to solve a challenge creatively.
- **Challenge-givers:** Organisations, companies, or individuals who proposed specific challenges or problem statements for participants to address during the Makeathon. They defined the problems, objectives, and requirements of the challenges, providing participants with a clear focus for their solution development.
- **Mentors:** Experts or professionals with specialised knowledge who provided guidance, feedback, and advice to participants, helping them refine their ideas and navigate challenges.
- **Judges:** A panel of experts who assess and evaluate the solutions based on the evaluation guidelines, and provide feedback and appreciation to all teams.

The handbook also helped to refine the format as it was discussed by the Work Package Board and all the organising parties during the initial planning stage.

2. Communication Plan

The communication plan included the key visuals for the event, the joint hashtag to be used as well as an overview of when to start communicating on the event and in which channels (for more details see B. Communication and Visibility).

3. Script

The script provided a minute-by-minute programme of all live-streamed parts of the Makeathon. During the livestream, connections with all cities as well as the virtual track were made from the moderation headquarter in Jena. The script ensured that all partners knew when it was their turn to speak and present.

B. Communication and visibility

A communication strategy was developed, including a key visual and a characteristic pink colour in addition to the EC2U brand identity. Templates for digital and printed materials were provided and could be adapted to the local requirements.

The Makeathon was promoted on ec2u.eu with a news page. In addition, some local university websites had it as event (e.g., uni-jena.de). Moreover, the event was advertised through the official EC2U social media accounts (LinkedIn, Instagram, Facebook) and through the networks of the universities, partners, challenge-givers (JenaVersum network, INVEST Research Flagship, Neoloji Technopole Grand Poitiers, etc.) and EC2U student alumni.

The central webpage is available at [this link](#).

Communication activities by the Universities of [Coimbra](#), [Iasi](#), [Jena](#), [Pavia](#), [Poitiers](#), and [Turku](#) happened on many channels, for example on websites, social media, email newsletters, posters, and local information screens.

On the [together.eu](#) platform, the Makeathon was added as event. Together.eu is an initiative run by the European Parliament dedicated to engaging as many people as possible involved in the European Union's democratic life.

The communication efforts were supported by the Makeathon partners and challenge-givers: [UC Business](#), [City of Jena](#), [Lichtwerkstatt Makerspace](#), [Neoloji Technopole Grand Poitiers](#), [INVEST Flagship](#), just to mention a few.

Figure 1: Local adaptations of the Makeathon key visuals, used for communication on social media.

EC2U Alliance
9. April · 🌐

🚀 Ready to tackle challenges and ignite change? Join the #EC2U #Makeathon now! Registration for online and local events is open! Check out the list of inspiring challenges related to:

- 🌱 Wellbeing & Happiness
- 🌍 Diversity & Inclusion
- 🌿 Nature & Sustainability
- 🗳️ Peace & Democracy

Get ready to make a difference! 🙌 <https://ec2u.eu/news/makeathon/>

Turun yliopisto - University of Turku - Universität Jena - Universidad de Salamanca - Universidade de Coimbra - Université de Poitiers - Università degli studi di Pavia - Universitatea „Alexandru Ioan Cuza” din Iași

Makeathon
Reinvent the future!

6-7 May 2024

📍 across Europe
in Coimbra, Iași, Jena, Pavia,
Poitiers, Salamanca, and Turku

Join in!

EC2U | RI4C2
Research & Innovation
For Cities & Citizens

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101035803.

15 11 Mal geteilt

EC2U Alliance
1,391 followers
1mo · 🌐

🌟 The Makeathon Awards have left their mark at our Jena makerspace and are now ready to journey across Europe! 🗺️ They'll be making stops in EC2U cities! Do you wish to claim one of these fantastic awards? Here's your chance! Register now for the Makeathon and take on a challenge alongside your team! Learn more about the Makeathon and sign up here: <https://lnkd.in/dJRjEw73>

Huge thanks to LICHTWERKSTATT JENA – Open Photonics Makerspace for their invaluable assistance with the awards!

This initiative is part of the "Research and Innovation for Cities and Citizens" (RI4C2) project by the EC2U Alliance, supported by the Horizon2020 programme of the European Union.

#Makeathon #Innovation #Collaboration #EC2U

Université de Poitiers | Università di Pavia | Friedrich Schiller University Jena | Universidad de Salamanca | Universidade de Coimbra | Universitatea „Alexandru Ioan Cuza” din Iași | Turun yliopisto - University of Turku

You and 33 others 1 comment · 4 reposts

Makeathon
Reinvent the future!
6-7 May 2024

6 May	Monday
14:00-15:00	Welcome and Opening
15:00-16:00	Local orientation and warm-up
	Teamworking time
16:30-17:00	European check-in
7 May	Tuesday
	Teamworking time
11:00-11:30	European check-in
	Teamworking time
14:00-15:00	Local presentations
15:00-16:30	Grand Finale
16:30-17:00	Awards and Celebration

© 2023 EC2U Alliance. All rights reserved. Terms & Conditions: <https://ec2u.eu/terms-conditions/>
📄 Click to expand with the original author's content.
🔒 Rights reserved and open to a broader audience.

ec2u.eu/makeathon

ec2u alliance 🚀 Get ready for an exhilarating experience! Join us for the Makeathon and unleash your creativity!

💡 To gear you up for 24 hours of intense team brainstorming, we're offering a preparatory training programme! Don't miss out! Register by April 28th and dive into the excitement! Click the link in bio to sign up! #Makeathon #Innovation #Creativity

📍 🗨 📌

Gefällt 41 Mal
26. April

Figure 2: Makeathon posts by the EC2U Alliance on different social media platforms

III. Trainings

Three online trainings and one industry insight were offered in the week before the Makeathon, to prepare the participants.

PITCH - How to Convince Your Audience

April 29th at 10:00-11:00 CEST

with Pekka Stenholm, Researcher and Trainer in Entrepreneurship, University of Turku

Industry Insight: Artificial Intelligence for a Sustainable Future

April 29th at 11:00-11:30 CEST

with Elena Romero Caamaño, Senior Innovation Manager and Rafael San Juan, Global Innovation Manager from Iberdrola

ENGAGE - How to Include Relevant Stakeholder Groups

April 29th at 12:00-12:30 CEST

with Jorge Hernandez, EC2U Communication Officer, University of Salamanca

PROTOTYPE - How to Bring Your Ideas to Reality

April 30th at 14:00-15:00 CEST

with David Zakoth, Open Innovation Expert at Lichtwerkstatt Makerspace, University of Jena

IV. The Makeathon events

A. Overview

The Makeathon happened in seven tracks (six cities and one virtual track) in parallel, and it was important for the organising teams to create a uniting pan-European experience. Therefore, a joint programme was designed with joint hybrid sessions, a joint digital infrastructure including a slack chat, similar decoration of the venues and awards.

Figure 3: The seven tracks connected by the European live sessions

Figure 4: The hybrid Check-in to connect with the other locations

Figure 5: The star awards, one for each local winner

Makeathon

Reinvent the future!

6-7 May 2024

6 May	Monday	
14:00-15:00	Welcome and Opening	●
15:00-16:00	Local orientation and warm-up	
	Teamworking time	
16:30-17:00	European check-in	●
7 May	Tuesday	
	Teamworking time	
11:00-11:30	European check-in	●
	Teamworking time	
14:00-15:00	Local presentations	
15:00-16:30	Grand Finale	●
16:30-17:00	Awards and Celebration	

All times in Central European Summer Time (CEST).
14:00 CEST equals 15:00 in Turku and Iasi and 13:00 in Coimbra.

- Hybrid, to connect with the other Makeathon locations across Europe.
- Hybrid and open to a broader audience.

ec2u.eu/makeathon

Figure 6: The programme of the Makeathon

The Makeathon locations across Europe were connected for the Opening, the two Check-ins, and the Grand Finale.

Opening

The opening started with a welcome from Dana Strauß, leader and main moderator of the Makeathon, and Ludovic Thilly, General Coordinator of the EC2U Alliance, and a Hello from each Makeathon location. The general goal of the event and the programme were presented.

Check-ins

There were two European check-ins, one at 16:30 on the first day and one at 11:00 on the second day. There, all locations and their teams connected virtually and gave a glimpse onto

what was happening there. These check-ins allowed to structure the teamwork and to create the feeling of a European connectedness.

Presentations and Finale

All solutions and teams who made it to the finish line were celebrated and received their individual award category. However, some selection at local level was needed since there were too many ideas to present them at the European level. Therefore, after the local presentations, the local juries nominated the “Local Winning Team” to present again at the Grand Finale of the Makeathon and at the Launch of PEKE in Poitiers. The members of the juries were given guidelines and an evaluation sheet, giving up to 10 points in the categories: Desirable, Feasible, and Viable and suggesting a unique feature as individual award category.

At the Grand Finale, each of the 7 local winners presented again and all participants could get an impression on what the teams from other locations have achieved. During each pitch, questions and feedback could be given via a QR Code. At the end, the audience was invited to vote for the “Winner of Hearts”. This was primarily an audience-engaging activity and did not have the goal to identify an overall “global winner” as collaboration, not competition, was at the heart of the Makeathon.

A general reporting article is available on the [EC2U website](#).

B. Coimbra

Event location: Institute of Interdisciplinary Research of the University of Coimbra, Polo II 3030-789 Coimbra

Organising team: Rita Martins dos Santos, Pâmela Aguiar, Jorge Noro, and Ana Beatriz Marques

Moderator: Rita Martins dos Santos

“Isolation” Challenge

How can digital technologies and innovation be agents for combating the isolation of rural populations, for example in terms of access to health care, medicines, therapies, among others, apart from combating loneliness through classic social media and/or communication technologies?

Challenge-giver: Instituto Pedro Nunes, Coimbra

Developed solution: The participants structured their solution based on the use of infrastructures that usually already exist in these more isolated locations, such as old schools, community centres, churches, etc. From these structures, previously equipped with digital tools, it would be possible to set up a community support service, for example, to book medical appointments, use digital channels from banks, insurance companies, connect with family/friends remotely, among others, and at the same time create a moment of companionship. This service could be contracted out by state structures such as town halls and local management bodies and/or private organisations such as day-care centres and nursing homes.

“Food” Challenge*

New public policies or educational programmes to promote healthy eating habits and physical activity from an early age, while also considering effective measures to combat food waste, such as those conducted on a daily basis by the big food retail companies in Portugal.

Challenge-giver: Institute of Interdisciplinary Research Team (University of Coimbra)

Developed solution: Seeds on Wheels (SOW) is a transformative movement in the realm of food education and awareness that operates through pop-up events and tactical placemaking. Their mission is to propel the transition towards healthy, sustainable, and local diets in collaboration with local institutions, businesses, and authorities. By fostering better practices within communities, they aim to bridge the gap between sustainable local businesses, changemakers, and consumers. SOW functions as a dynamic hub, adapting to local needs and agendas, fostering synergies and cultivating new connections within communities through curated community events, and the establishment of an online platform.

*Local winner of the University of Coimbra

“School failure” Challenge

Which role can the University and/or Governmental Organisations play in preventing school failure among basic level students living in socio-economically underprivileged conditions?

Challenge-giver: EqualSteam Project Team

Developed solution: The participants imagined a network in which, on the one hand, university students from various fields would provide school support to these children using the primary schools where they were already studying and, on the other hand, they would raise awareness among the higher education academic community to collect goods (calculators, backpacks, school supplies, books, etc.). The match between child and university student would be made according to the area and/or areas of study in which the child had the most difficulty, and each child could be matched with more than one university student.

Figure 7: Photos from the Makeathon in Coimbra

C. Iași

Event location: UAIC Main Building, Bd. Carol I, 11, 707506 Iași

Organising team: Ana Iolanda Voda, Ionel Mangalagiu, Adriana Zait, Laura Hrostea, Iustinian Bejan, Alina Morosanu, Cornelia Mairean, Elena Radu, Diana Lina, Elida Rosenhech, Sergiu Bortos, Carmen Moldovan, Mihaela Carausu, and Mihaela Mocanu

Moderator: Laura Hrosea

In Romania, the European Week coincided with the Orthodox Easter holiday this year: the 6th of May was Orthodox Easter Monday. This impacted the number of participants and the range of challenges that could be offered.

“Teleportation – Engage” Challenge

How can we find better transportation solutions, to decongest traffic, to reduce time spent in traffic, to reduce pollution?

Challenge tackled: Traffic congestion is more than just a time waster; it is an urban problem with multiple dimensions that includes resource depletion and pollution. The causes of traffic congestion depend on the actors involved. Citizens' individual preferences for comfort and convenience certainly play a role, but the underlying factors are much more complex. An old infrastructure heavily reliant on automobile usage, coupled with inflexible work schedules and poorly coordinated construction projects, creates a system prone to congestion. This complex set of problems is likely to worsen and threaten the long-term viability of our cities unless significant investments are made in robust public transportation networks and forward-thinking urban planning strategies are implemented.

Solution developed: The Iași team's "Teleportation - Engage" solution gamifies sustainable transportation through a mobile app where the reward system encourages the use of alternate modes of transportation. Bonus points could be earned for walking, cycling, or taking public transportation. These points could then give right to a discount on fares for public transport tickets and passes, offers at a selection of shops, free access to cultural events, etc. This programme aims to create a collaborative effort involving local government, businesses, and residents. Additionally, the system employs generative AI and augmented reality as a lens through which

to view the past. This can inspire individuals to travel to their destination, gather points, and take the time to learn about the history of their surroundings.

Follow-up reporting from the Alexandru Ioan Cuza University of Iasi is available on their [website](#).

Figure 8: Photos from the Makeathon in Iasi

D. Jena

Event location: StadtLab Jena, Löbderstraße 6, 07743 Jena

Organising team: Dana Strauß, Sophia-Marie Meyer, and Christin Unterbeck

Moderator: Dana Strauß

“Trees” Challenge

Raising awareness on the importance of trees for the local climate and heat stress protection.

Challenge-giver: Bettina Böhm, Research Associate in Geoinformation Science, University of Jena and Laura Brock, Climate protection manager, Green Office of the University of Jena.

Developed solution: Participants proposed a multifaceted approach to address this challenge. They suggested launching a campaign titled "Jungle to the Concrete" featuring posters to visually communicate the significance of trees. Additionally, they recommended the installation of portable trees in urban areas, complemented by technological interventions such as interactive

displays and augmented reality (AR) tools for educational purposes. QR codes would be deployed to provide access to further information and encourage participation in related projects. The initiative is set to be supported by sponsorship from entities like Stadtwerke Jena, sustainable companies, and AR/VR firms.

“Data for Cities” Challenge

Navigating the plethora of information available to citizens due to the fragmentation of data across various platforms and websites.

Challenge-giver: Stefan Schwarz, City of Jena, as part of the Smart City project

Developed solution: The proposed solution involves the implementation of a Chat System tailored specifically for Jena. This system aims to streamline access to information by providing a unified platform for citizens to interact with and receive relevant data.

“Education Bike” Challenge*

Addressing social divisions through digital education initiatives.

Challenge-giver: Sandra Laue, Volkshochschule Jena (community college) and Bärbel Kracke, Professor of Educational Psychology, University of Jena

Developed solution: Participants put forward a holistic approach to promote digital education and foster a sense of community. Their strategy includes initiatives aimed at making digital education accessible to everyone, irrespective of their background. This encompasses various measures such as issuing internet licenses, facilitating equipment rental, offering real-time translation services, and ensuring accessibility options for people with disabilities. The ultimate goal is to cultivate media literacy and promote inclusivity through localised projects.

**Local winner of the University of Jena*

“Digital Innovation Hub” Challenge

Presenting innovative solutions directly to the challenge-giver.

Challenge-giver: Dominique Dölz, Jena Digital e.V.

Developed solution: The participants presented their solutions exclusively to the challenge-giver. It included a watering system for indoor greens and a privacy room that can be used for telephone calls, but also for breastfeeding or calming down children or getting a relaxing break for people with ADHS or social anxiety.

Figure 9: Photos from the Makeathon in Jena

E. Pavia

Event location: Polo Tecnologico, Via Fratelli Cuzio, 42, 27100 Pavia PV, Italy

Organising team: Daniela Ovadia, Gaia Garancini, and Dalila Formica

Moderator: Daniela Ovadia

“Safe campus” Challenge

How to enhance the safety and security on university campuses in Italy, addressing issues of harassment and violence?

Challenge-giver: Union of University Students, Pavia

Developed solution: prototype an AI signal detector to be installed in university premises and to be activated in case of need using body signals or dedicated keyword. The signal detector would be integrated with a dedicated app for registration.

“Working mothers” Challenge

How to improve work-life balance with a focus on policies that support female employment and family-work reconciliation in Italy?

Challenge-giver: Municipality of Pavia

Developed solution: Creation of coworking space with childcare, based on public funds and volunteering, with the aim to promote remote working, provide a safe space for parents to leave their children, foster gender equality, and allow to manage time more effectively.

“International students housing” Challenge*

How to address the housing crisis affecting international students, exacerbated by high demand, unfamiliar rental processes, and financial constraints?

Challenge-giver: International Mobility unit - University of Pavia

Developed solution: Create a synergy between hosting institution, local municipalities and university dormitories to implement key actions such as implementing dormitory stay restrictions, creating a housing contracts knowledge base and verification system, enhancing financial safety measures, and developing an official peer recommendation system for housing. The project emphasises on creating a verified housing hub, guiding housing contract terms in the local language, and promoting trust and transparency to ensure a safe and inclusive housing environment for international students.

**Local winner of the University of Pavia*

“EU Elections” Challenge

How to increase European citizenship and sense of belonging among the EC2U student community?

Challenge-giver: International Mobility unit University of Pavia

Developed solution: A multitude of measures were proposed, including lowering the voting age, promoting young candidates, raising awareness among young people, and involving young people in the decision-making process.

Sustainable cosmetics

How to enhance sustainability in the cosmetics industry, particularly focusing on the management of post-use cosmetic packaging?

Challenge giver: ETICHUB - Pavia private company

Developed solution: Conceive the external part of the packaging like a post parcel. The customer buys the cosmetic product in a box that is already set like a postal package, ready to be taken to a post office or to a tobacco shop and that contains the address of the agency that treats the specific kind of material waste which the cosmetics packaging in question are made of. Boxes also include an attractive design and statements in order to make the customer aware of the issue of cosmetics waste and the importance to differentiate these wasted materials. With

this strategy, the customer is aware and encouraged not to throw away the cosmetic packaging in a common bin, thanks to the ease of the operation.

Follow-up reporting from the University of Pavia is available on their [website](#).

Figure 10: Photos from the Makeathon in Pavia

F. Poitiers

Event location: QG Sport Santé, 1 Boulevard Lavoisier, 86360 Chasseneuil-du-Poitou, France

Organising team: Pauline Bordiec, Ancis Georges, and Elif Gulsen

Moderator: Pauline Bordiec

“Rain water for urban cool islands” Challenge*

How could rain water be collected to supply urban cool islands?

Challenge-giver: Fondation Poitiers Université, Thierry Ferreira

Developed solution: Water storage systems on top of buildings and behind green walls to cool down buildings and supply water during heatwaves. Decorative metallic structures covered by greenery that include a water storage and phytoremediation system and provide shadowing. The goal is for this idea to be integrated into the IDEA programme of the Poitiers University Foundation and to collaborate with relevant local stakeholders to implement these devices in EC2U cities.

**Local Winner of the University of Poitiers*

“Physical activity promotion programmes” Challenge

Alone we go faster, together we go further. How could the different stakeholders of a territory be involved in the co-conception of physical activity promotion programmes?

Challenge-giver: Sport and Health Chair of the University of Poitiers, Prof. Laurent Bosquet.

Developed solution: Connect companies with relevant local stakeholders (e.g., architects, physical activity professionals, etc.) to implement a physically active lifestyle in companies.

“Young women’s experience in public space” Challenge

How could we make public space more welcoming for young women?

Challenge-giver: Info Jeunes Nouvelle Aquitaine - Europe Direct Poitiers Vienne / Deux Sèvres

Developed solution: Establish a non-profit organisation that creates video clips raising awareness about the issue of women's harassment in public space.

“Taking care of hospital patients” Challenge

How could patients be better taken care of despite the lack of hospital staff?

Challenge-giver: Neoloji Technopole Grand Poitiers

Developed solution: A single national digital platform for administrative procedures, exchanges between patients and staff, patient data storage and staff training (e.g. file consultation, appointments, staff schedules, medical reports, etc.). Some administrative procedures, such as planning the staff schedule or writing medical reports, are supported by Artificial Intelligence to increase efficiency.

Figure 11: Photos from the Makeathon in Poitiers

G. Salamanca

Unfortunately, the sudden resignation of the University of Salamanca Rector placed a new electoral process in motion, which resulted in elections on the 7th of May, date over which the organisation team had no control on. That day and the preceding Reflection Day on the 6th of May, no activities that could be connected with the candidates were allowed to take place, according to the electoral board (Junta Electoral). Therefore, the on-site Makeathon event in Salamanca had to be cancelled on the 3rd of April by instructions of the electoral Board. Indeed, the Vice-Rector for Internationalisation, who is one of the few Vice-Rectors that will transition from the previous rectoral team to the newly elected team, is very connected to the EC2U Alliance activities. Moreover, the electoral board was to use the university premises to organise the election.

However, the central Makeathon coordinators have still welcomed students and citizens from Salamanca to participate in the virtual European track. The University of Salamanca organising team supported the virtual track and the online training.

H. Turku

Event location: Entrepreneurial Hub Konttori, Hämeenkatu 9, 20500 Turku

Organising team: Maija Lespinasse and Laura Niemi

Moderator: Maija Lespinasse and Laura Niemi

“Meeting places” Challenge

How might we bring together people of different ages and backgrounds in a way that increases solidarity and inclusion?

Challenge-giver: City of Turku, mentored by Riitta Nieminen, Lundén Architecture Company

Developed solution: The Core COME TO LIFE! is a both on-site and virtual hub for people, which is built around communal square and phone application, suggesting things to do every day. Days are divided into themes, where people can join and meet each other. The facilities

are built with colourful site containers, making it easy to modify and move to a new location according to needs.

“Nature in Urban Planning” Challenge *

How might we recognise and consider the diverse values of nature in urban planning?

Challenge-giver: Department of Geography and Geology, University of Turku, mentored by Laura Niemi, University of Turku

Developed solution: Green Space Takeover is an effort to make use of urban areas which are not actively in use by cities. The act starts by city recognising green urban spaces as assets and by lining which areas should be developed. Then organisations can apply to “adopt” areas and provide development plan for that area, and finally the citizens and residents will vote for the winning “adoption plan”.

**Local winner of the University of Turku*

“Equal educational opportunities” Challenge

How can we ensure equal educational opportunities for young people finishing elementary school in different (also distant) areas of Finland?

Challenge-giver: INVEST Research Flagship Centre, mentored by Lassi Yli-Muilu, University of Turku

Developed solution: Locally networked learning environments include municipality-wide hybrid classrooms to equalise teaching content. Also, networking nationally or even internationally is made possible. Three types of teaching are available by national broadcasted lectures, by online-available subject matter teachers, and by local onsite teachers in class rooms.

“Reducing loneliness” Challenge

What societal measures could be taken to reduce loneliness?

Challenge-giver: INVEST Research Flagship Centre, mentored by Lauri Koittola, BOOST Turku and Aschwin van der Woude, Vincit

Developed solution: Seura platform is an online application which gathers events arranged by already existing organisations and classifies the events according to different themes and keywords. The events are also pinpointed to a map where the user can see the ones taking place nearby.

Follow-up reporting from the University of Turku is available on their [website](#).

Figure 12: Photos from the Makeathon in Turku

I. Virtual track

Event location: As virtual “location”, a Slack collaboration platform was used. All “local” programme points could be done similarly via Slack, with chat and videocall tools.

Organising team: Eleonore Roderfeld and Ricardo Costa

Moderator: Ricardo Costa (USAL)

“Meeting places” Challenge

How might we bring together people of different ages and backgrounds in a way that increases solidarity and inclusion?

Challenge-giver: City of Turku, mentored by Maija Rusanen from the Kupittaa project.

Developed solution: "Friendship Square" is bringing people together in an environment where everyone can feel welcome, explore new interests, and build lasting relationships. With multiple activities and facilities around the harmony concept of earth, fire, water, and air.

"Science communication" Challenge*

How can we make science more accessible and combat science scepticism and conspiracy theories?

Challenge-giver: JenaVersum e.V., mentored by Magdalena Voll, Communication and Marketing at JenaVersum.

Developed solution: "Science Bridge" aims at making science more accessible by giving voice to workers from various industries and experts of practice. For example, a farmer observing climate change or a nurse explaining vaccinations and infectious diseases.

**Local winner of the virtual European track*

Figure 13: Collage with screenshots from the virtual track.

V. Follow-up activities

It was highlighted that all the Makeathon outcomes are valuable and may develop further, and that all involved actors are warmly invited to build up on the momentum and the awareness raised by the Makeathon.

There were some self-organised follow-up meetings and individual continuation. For example, a week after the Makeathon, there was a meeting with the three members of the “Meeting places” team to present their idea again to the challenge-giver and her colleagues from the City of Turku. From the Poitiers track, the team on “Rain water for urban cool islands” deepened the collaboration with the challenge-giver “Fondation Poitiers Université” and is going to join the IDEA (Innover en Dehors du cAdre) programme of the Fondation Poitiers Université, a programme that invites multidisciplinary teams of teachers and students to work on general interest projects identified within the local territory.

Each of the seven winning teams was awarded with one “Ticket to Poitiers”, to present their idea and to further spread it at a European level during the conference “Unveiling the University of the Future: Kick off the EC2U Pan-European Knowledge Ecosystem” on 11-12 June 2024 (Deliverable D1.8). There, the selected participants presented their idea again as part of the main programme and worked on spreading their call to action, valorising the EC2U networks such as social media accounts, and email newsletters. The participants valued the experience to get together with peers from all over Europe.

VI. Evaluation

A. Quantitative feedback

The Makeathon participants were given the opportunity to provide feedback on the event twice: directly after the Grand Finale with the whole audience with an online poll, and around a week later with a more detailed feedback survey.

At the end of the Grand Finale, a direct poll was conducted with Slido. People were presented with a QR code that they could scan in order to take part in the poll. The question 'How do you like the Makeathon event?' was answered by 70 people. On a satisfaction scale of 1-5, a satisfaction score of 4.5 stars and a satisfaction rate of 90% was achieved.

Similarly, in the later feedback survey, participants, challenge-givers, partners and mentors gave 4.5 stars on average with a satisfaction rate of 92 %.

Figure 14: Satisfaction rating

Figure 15: Survey results about identifying the most important aspects of the Makeathon

B. Quotes from participants

The following quotes show qualitative feedback from the participants that was given after the Grand Finale in the feedback survey or on social media.

*“The most **valuable experience** was to get out of my comfort zone working on a real-world related challenge, working with teammates I didn't previously know and speaking in public.” - Participant from Pavia*

*“I feel valued and that my proposals will serve a **purpose**.” - Participant from Poitiers (translated from French)*

“Even if you don't believe something in the beginning, you can make it happen. Don't do it for the applause, do it for the cause.” - Participant from Jena

“I really enjoyed the collaborative experience within the team, whether it was working with the other participants or interacting with the mentors. These interactions

were more than enriching, both professionally and personally.” - Participant from Poitiers (translated from French)

“**Excellent experience** to work with people outside your own university faculty and learn new insights from them.” - Participant from Turku

“The most valuable insight for me during the Makeathon was the **power of collaboration and diverse perspectives**. Seeing how different minds came together to tackle a problem from various angles was truly inspiring and taught me the importance of teamwork in innovation.” - Participant from Iasi

“The event was **flawlessly organized**, creating an environment that fostered creativity and teamwork. We are especially thankful for the invaluable feedback from the judges and the enthusiastic support from fellow participants, which has provided us with new perspectives and ways to improve our project. [...]” - Participant from Pavia on LinkedIn

“[...] We are excited about the new connections we've made and the potential collaborations that lie ahead. Looking forward to participating in future events and continuing this journey of innovation and discovery as a team.” - Participant from Pavia on LinkedIn

Figure 16: Public post of a participant from Turku

Vittoria Cozzatelli • 2.
BSc in Business Administration
2 Wochen • Bearbeitet •

+ Folgen ...

I had an incredible experience at the first [#Makeathon](#) launched by [EC2U Alliance](#) on May 6th-7th. This event brought together local organizations that posed challenges related to real-world issues and individuals eager to solve them. The purpose of this initiative is to unleash students' creativity and allow them to develop innovative projects to better our cities and future, implementing a solution within 24 hours.

Me and my team worked on the "Campus as a safe space" challenge, conceiving a security system prototype to enhance safety in college facilities. I'm glad I had the opportunity to take part in such a stimulating event! Special thanks to [Università di Pavia](#) and [EC2U Alliance](#) for the organization and to my supportive teammates [ANDREA GIACOMELLI](#) and [Emna BENMANSOUR](#) for the collaboration. We accomplished great work together!

Looking forward to tackle more challenges like this in the future!

Sie und 22 weitere Personen

2 Kommentare • 1 direkt geteilter Beitrag

Figure 17: Public post of a participant from Pavia

C. Quotes from challenge-givers and partners

The following quotes show qualitative feedback from the partners and challenge-givers that was given after the Grand Finale via the feedback survey, email, or social media.

*“Thank you for involving us in this event. It was a very well-organised initiative and I believe it was an **excellent experience** of enrichment for all the students who participated: congratulations! The students who took on our challenge worked very well, and this is even more true if we take into account the little time available to deepen their knowledge of the topic; they developed an interesting proposal and we were very happy to have accompanied them on their journey.” - Challenge-giver from Pavia*

*“It was a **challenging and rewarding experience**. It was a pleasure to participate in an event that brought together such a variety of people and created a vibrant environment for sharing. It was certainly an **excellent starting point** for any future editions of the event.” - Challenge-giver from Pavia*

*“We are thrilled by so much community, creativity and team spirit across national borders. Another innovative format for our city and Europe that was a **complete success**. Thank you to everyone involved!” - City of Jena on LinkedIn (translated from German)*

“It was really an interesting experience and the teams were really motivated. The virtual track worked surprisingly well and the slack platform worked surprisingly well for this. The atmosphere in the event was really nice and organisers really helpful.” - Challenge-giver and mentor from the virtual track

“I met an international team who really impressed me. Their ability to immediately start working on the challenge was remarkable.” - Partner, mentor, or jury member from Turku

*“Passing on my good entrepreneurial practices and **encouraging people** to want to be entrepreneurs is what has enriched me as a mentor.” - Mentor from Poitiers*

“Hearing the pitch and great ideas from the team that I mentored. They had worked so well in the short period of time and had really good and inspiring ideas for how to develop cities for people.” - Challenge-giver and mentor from the virtual track

VII. Lessons learned

The evaluation indicates that the Makeathon met its objectives, generating innovation through collaboration and reinforcing the EC2U community's commitment to re-inventing the future in line with the UNSDGs.

However, we recognise that citizen participation was lower than anticipated, with only 4 registrations from the general public, 20 university staff registrations, and 126 student registrations. This might be due to the novel format of the event, which positions participants as co-creators rather than passive listeners. While this approach has its merits it may require more time and effort to attract broader citizen involvement.

Another challenge were no-shows and drop-outs. Despite receiving 150 registrations, only 72 participants actually attended the event. Some individuals informed the organisers of scheduling conflicts or illnesses, leading them to withdraw their participation. Presumably, others may have felt hesitant about the format and the time commitment required. These no-shows complicated the team formation, resulting in some challenges not having enough team members. Nonetheless, those who attended were highly engaged and significantly contributed to the success of the Makeathon. To improve future participation to such a novel event format, we suggest using, authentic photos, quotes, and alumni support from the pilot event to provide a clearer impression of the format. Additionally, as no-shows are inevitable, we recommend maintaining the flexible processes, especially in the team formation, to accommodate this. Moreover, while the high number of challenges submitted demonstrates the potential for future Makeathons, focusing on fewer challenges next time could allow for deeper exploration or diverse solution paths for the same challenge.

VIII. Conclusion

The EC2U/RI4C2 Makeathon brought together participants from diverse backgrounds across Europe to integrate efforts and co-create solutions together. It included events in six locations, each contributing unique challenges and solutions, from Jena to Coimbra, Iași, Pavia, Poitiers, Salamanca, Turku, and the virtual track. Through thorough preparation and effective communication, significant engagement and visibility were achieved, leading to a dynamic event. The Makeathon has established a solid foundation for promoting continuous innovation through collaboration within the EC2U Pan-European Knowledge Ecosystem, taking meaningful steps toward a more interconnected future and social change.

IX. Annexes

A. Annex A: EC2U Makeathon form (registration form with challenges offered)

Looking forward to co-creating with you! Across Europe, in Coimbra, Iasi, Jena, Pavia, Poitiers, Turku and Salamanca at the same time.

The EC2U Makeathon is an engaging and interactive event that brings together people and local organisations to collaboratively develop creative solutions. Our joint goal is the creation and implementation of ideas that solve local challenges and contribute to a better future.

In a guided process, participants will be enabled to form teams around relevant local challenges and to develop first solutions together. A preparatory workshop programme is offered and experts support the teams. The main event will be on 6 May afternoon and 7 May morning and afternoon. It takes place at all EC2U cities simultaneously.

Please register by 28 April. We will send you an email with further details then.

More information on the Makeathon website: <https://ec2u.eu/makeathon/>

If you would like to take an active role in the Makeathon as partner or challenge-giver, please reach out to ec2u@uni-jena.de

* necessary

About this registration form

We have asked different local partners to submit relevant challenges, fostering democracy, wellbeing, inclusion, and sustainability. Now, we need creative participants to tackle these challenges and to come up with creative solutions!

Basically, there are two modes of participation:

- The local track in your city. You will be on-side and meet your team in-person.
- The virtual European track. You can connect from wherever you are. You will collaborate online with participants from across Europe.

Here, you will be able to read about all challenges available and give your preferences. If you are not interested in one mode of participation at all, you can just skip the page.

There will also be a About yourself section, where we would like to get to know you a little. So let's go!

1

Your email address *

So that we can contact you with an invitation to the EC2U Makeathon.

[text field]

2

Which EC2U city do you belong to? *

Coimbra (Portugal); Iași (Romania); Jena (Germany); Pavia (Italy); Poitiers (France); Salamanca (Spain); Turku (Finland); new EC2U member Linz (Austria); associated EC2U member Lviv (Ukraine)

1. Poitiers Challenges

Event location: QG Sport Santé, 1 Bd Lavoisier, 86360 Chasseneuil-du-Poitou, France

Contact person: Anaïs Georges (University of Poitiers)

Here, you find the local challenges. Later, we will match you with one challenge and around 3 other participants. Together as new team, you will tackle the challenge during the Makeathon event!

Please give your preferences regarding the challenges.

Your favourite one ★★★

Your second favourite one ★★

Give only 1 star (★) to all challenges that you are okay to take part in it, in case your preferences are not available. If you give no star to a challenge, it means you are not interested at all.

10

Prise en charge des patients à l'hôpital

Thématique : Bonne santé et bien-être Institution : Technopole Grand Poitiers

Comment mieux prendre en charge les patients face au manque de personnel à l'hôpital ?

11

Expérience des jeunes femmes dans l'espace public

Thématique : Diversité et inclusion

Institution : Centre Europe Direct Poitiers Vienne / Deux Sèvres | Info Jeunes Nouvelle Aquitaine

Comment rendre l'espace public plus accueillant pour les jeunes femmes ?

12

Engagement des jeunes pour le climat et l'environnement

Thématique : Nature et développement durable

Institution : Centre Europe Direct Poitiers Vienne / Deux Sèvres | Info Jeunes Nouvelle Aquitaine

Comment encourager l'engagement des jeunes autour des enjeux climatiques et environnementaux ?

13

Sensibilisation au consentement et prévention des violences sexuelles

Thématique : Diversité et inclusion

Institution : Association Le P'tit Prince

Comment sensibiliser dès le plus jeune âge au sujet du consentement et à la prévention des comportements problématiques pouvant engendrer des violences sexuelles ?

14

Promotion de l'activité physique dans les territoires

Thématique : Bonne santé et bien-être

Institution : Chaire Sport Santé

Seul on va plus vite, ensemble on va plus loin. Comment impliquer les différents acteurs d'un territoire dans la co-conception de programmes de promotion de l'activité physique ?

15

Protection de la biodiversité et des conditions de la vie humaine

Thématique : Nature et développement durable

Institution : Technopole Grand Poitiers

Comment adapter nos modes de vie pour limiter la dégradation de la biodiversité et ses conséquences sur la vie humaine ? (ex. dérégulation des populations d'insectes qui menace la sécurité alimentaire, la santé humaine, etc.) ?

16

Participation citoyenne

Thématique : Paix et démocratie Institution : Grand Poitiers

Comment inciter les publics éloignés de la vie publique à prendre part aux instances de participation citoyenne ?

17

Ilots de fraîcheur urbains

Thématique : Nature et développement durable

Institution : Fondation Poitiers Université

Comment collecter les eaux pluviales pour alimenter des îlots de fraîcheur urbains ?

2. Pavia Challenges

Event location: Polo Tecnologico, Via Fratelli Cuzio, 42, 27100 Pavia PV, Italy

Contact person: Gaia Garancini (University of Pavia)

Here, you find the local challenges. Later, we will match you with one challenge and around 3 other participants. Together as new team, you will tackle the challenge during the Makeathon event!

Please give your preferences regarding the challenges.

Your favourite one ★★★

Your second favourite one ★★

Give only 1 star (★) to all challenges that you are okay to take part in it, in case your preferences are not available. If you give no star to a challenge, it means you are not interested at all.

18

Working mothers

Area: Diversity and Inclusion

Challenge-giver: Municipality of Pavia

In our country, there is also a gap in the ratio of men to women in the labour market. One in five women leave the labour market as a result of motherhood. This last aspect is of particular relevance as an indication of the difficulty for women to balance family and work life.

Being well understood that this situation requires huge and structural measures to be solved at a systemic and national level, how might we facilitate families to find a work-life balance that allows especially women to regain an active work life after motherhood? For example, in the city of Pavia, how can public institutions and public companies support mothers in coming back to work and to sustain a good work-life balance?

19

Campus as safe space

Area: Diversity and Inclusion

Challenge-giver: Union of University Students, Pavia

The gender-related safety and security (real or perceived) of Italian University campuses is an issue.

According to a recent study carried out in Italy by UDU (Unione degli Universitari) concerning this matter, 20.5% of respondents think that these are not safe spaces, while 34.5% have heard of cases of harassment or violence within university premises.

How might we contribute to making our campus a safe space for everybody? Which concrete actions can be put in place to advocate for systemic, structural measures on this side, as well as to raise awareness on the importance of respect, non-discrimination and inclusiveness in our university?

20

International students housing

Area: Wellbeing and happiness

Challenge giver: International Mobility unit - University of Pavia

As indicated in the Statement of the European Students' Union and Erasmus Student Network on Housing and Transport, 'Housing is an essential part of a student's life, as without this basic need being fulfilled, there is no capacity to study'. The student housing situation in Europe is facing increasing challenges, which are not just the result of the Covid-19 pandemic and of the recent inflation surge but are ingrained in long-term trends. This is particularly relevant for international mobile students since temporary stays are even more affected by the current crisis, the transient nature of student exchanges, typically lasting for one or two semesters, discouraging landlords from offering contracts to students.

Being well understood that this situation requires huge and structural measures to be solved at a systemic level, which innovative solutions or approaches can be suggested to ease the existing situation or to advocate for innovative solutions to this problem? How could these innovative solutions be applied, for example, in the city of Pavia?

21

Sustainable cosmetics

Area: Nature and Sustainability

Challenge giver: ETICHUB - Pavia private company

Sustainability in cosmetics and better management of post-use cosmetic packaging is the challenge. This challenge is highly relevant for the future, given the increasing awareness of environmental issues and the growing consumer demand for sustainable products. Responsible packaging management is crucial to reduce the environmental impact of plastic waste and promote more eco-friendly practices in the cosmetic industry and the consumer.

How can we effectively manage the disposal of cosmetic products to ensure they are truly recyclable? What local initiatives can be implemented on a smaller scale to initiate both awareness campaigns and practical actions?

3. Turku Challenges

Event location: Entrepreneurial Hub Konttori, Hämeenkatu 9, 20500 Turku

Contact person: Laura Niemi (University of Turku)

Here, you find the local challenges. Later, we will match you with one challenge and around 3 other participants. Together as new team, you will tackle the challenge during the Makeathon event!

Please give your preferences regarding the challenges.

Your favourite one ★★★

Your second favourite one ★★

Give only 1 star (★) to all challenges that you are okay to take part in it, in case your preferences are not available. If you give no star to a challenge, it means you are not interested at all.

22

Nature in urban planning

Area: Diversity and Inclusion

Challenge-giver: Department of Geography and Geology, University of Turku

How might we recognize and consider the diverse values of nature in urban planning?

23

Equal educational opportunities

Area: Diversity and Inclusion

Challenge-giver: INVEST Resarch Flagship Centre

How can we ensure equal educational opportunities for young people finishing elementary school in different areas of Finland? Every young person should have the possibility to participate in secondary education that suits their preferences, provides sufficient capabilities to succeed in the future, and offers good and fair preparation for higher education. By secondary education we refer to both high school and vocational school (ammattikoulu).

How could high-quality secondary education be provided in small towns with few young people? Could virtual reality opportunities, new forms of social benefits, or even new types of housing arrangements help in this regard? What should be taken into account and changed to ensure that young people have equal opportunities for education regardless of where they live?

24

Reducing loneliness

Area: Wellbeing and Happiness

Challenge-giver: INVEST Resarch Flagship Centre

According to research data, loneliness has increased significantly during past years in Finland, and in media loneliness seems to get the status of even an epidemic. Loneliness is both a personal and a societal problem because it is linked, for example, to bullying, alcoholism, health and mental health issues, as well as work-related stress. What societal measures could be taken to reduce loneliness?

Although loneliness is more common among, for example, the unemployed and the elderly, it occurs generally across all population groups, including those in relationships and those with large social networks. Loneliness is a subjective and negative experience resulting from quantitatively or qualitatively deficient relationships, thus distinguishing it from, for example, solitude, which can be a positive experience. Combating loneliness is not straightforward. It is not entirely clear whose "responsibility" it is to alleviate loneliness, and currently, many different actors, such as organizations, are striving to reduce people's perceived loneliness.

25

Meeting places for people

Area: Diversity and Inclusion

Challenge-giver: City of Turku

How might we bring together people of different ages and backgrounds in a way that increases solidarity and inclusion? It might be digital or material solutions.

The aim of Kupittaa Partnership Project (Kupittaa Core) Point is to provide meeting places for people. Bringing together people of different ages and backgrounds is one of the key aspects of the project. We address, among other things, discrimination, loneliness, and social exclusion. Furthermore, we support encounters that enhance the vitality of the city and the emergence of innovations.

4. Jena Challenges

Event location: Stadtlab Jena (in the city center), Löbderstraße 6, 07743 Jena

Languages: German and English

Contact person: Dana Strauß (University of Jena)

Here, you find the local challenges. Later, we will match you with one challenge and around 3 other participants. Together as new team, you will tackle the challenge during the Makeathon event!

Please give your preferences regarding the challenges.

Your favourite one ★★★

Your second favourite one ★★

Give only 1 star (★) to all challenges that you are okay to take part in it, in case your preferences are not available. If you give no star to a challenge, it means you are not interested at all.

26

Inclusive environments

Area: Diversity and Inclusion

Challenge-giver: Bärbel Kracke, Professor of Educational Psychology, University of Jena

How can the city be made physically and socio-culturally accessible? Our society is facing the major challenge that people's living environments are becoming increasingly divergent. We can only overcome this if there are conditions in which people with different abilities can meet. How can this be achieved?

27

Education Bike

Area: Diversity and Inclusion

Challenge-giver: Volkshochschule Jena

With our special bike, we want to create inclusive future education spaces especially on on digital skills and technologies. Specifically, a low-threshold opportunity to try out devices and applications. The aim is to reach many citizens to acquire basic digital skills.

How can this bike be technically equipped and decorated? E.g., with sustainable power supply, wifi, etc. How can different target groups be approached? And how can offers be made interactive?

28

Trees

Area: Nature and Sustainability

Challenge-giver: Bettina Böhm, Research Associate in Geoinformation Science, University of Jena

How might we raise awareness for the importance of trees in our city, especially for the local climate and protection against heat stress?

Climate change is causing heatwaves to occur much more frequently than in the past. The architecture of cities intensifies the heat and leads to heat stress for people. Trees that provide shade, green façades and roofs, and smaller parks cool by casting shade and by evaporation from the leaves.

29

Car-free city center

Area: Nature and Sustainability

Challenge-giver: Laura Brock, Climate protection manager, Green Office of the University of Jena

In order to maintain our quality of life locally and globally, we need to meet the climate targets. How might we convince people of drastic changes such as a car-free city centre in Jena? Using the example of a car-free city centre, how exactly could it be designed? Which people will be excessively negatively affected by these changes and how can we ensure that acceptable solutions are found for them while still pursuing the climate targets?

30

Data for cities

Area: Peace and Democracy

Challenge-giver: Stefan Schwarz, Stadtverwaltung Jena, als Teil des Smart City Projekts

How could we use the data from the WISSENSallmende and its intelligent linking with other information on the city's websites to solve problems for citizens, answer questions and create added value for science and business?

31

Digital Innovation Hub

Area: Nature and Sustainability Challenge-giver: Jena Digital e.V.

How can we design the Digital Innovation Hub in Jena so that it becomes an attractive point of contact for students on the topics of digitalization, innovation, transformation and participation?

5. Iași Challenges

Event location: UAIC Main Building, Bd. Carol I, 11, 707506 Iasi

Language: Romanian and English

Contact person: Adriana Zait (Alexandru Ioan Cuza University of Iași)

Here, you find the local challenges. Later, we will match you with one challenge and around 3 other participants. Together as new team, you will tackle the challenge during the Makeathon event!

Please give your preferences regarding the challenges.

Your favourite one ★★★

Your second favourite one ★★

Give only 1 star (★) to all challenges that you are okay to take part in it, in case your preferences are not available. If you give no star to a challenge, it means you are not interested at all.

32

We are Nature-all

Area: Nature and Sustainability

Challenge giver: Civica + RI4C2 WP5 team Iasi

How could we, as citizens, extend and protect green areas all around the city - home parks, streets, job places, own house? How can we educate people to love and protect nature, preserve it clean and beautiful?

33

Teleportation - engage!

Area: Wellbeing and Happiness

Challenge giver RI4C2 WP5 team Iasi

How can we find better transportation solutions, to decongest traffic, reduce time spent in traffic, reduce pollution?

34

Your city is as powerful as your involvement

Area: Peace and Democracy

Challenge giver: Civica

How can we increase civic participation, for all city issues? How can we educate citizens to be active, raise questions, suggest solutions for the city's challenges?

35

Regenerate the future

Area: Nature and Sustainability + Wellbeing and Happiness

Challenge giver: Iulius Group

How can we find the best urban regeneration solutions - for old industrial buildings, for poorer areas near the city, for ugly old apartment blocks?

6. Coimbra Challenges

Event location: Institute of Interdisciplinary Research of the University of Coimbra, Polo II 3030-789 Coimbra

Language: Portuguese and English

Contact person: Rita Martins dos Santos (University of Coimbra)

Here, you find the local challenges. Later, we will match you with one challenge and around 3 other participants. Together as new team, you will tackle the challenge during the Makeathon event!

Please give your preferences regarding the challenges.

Your favourite one ★★★

Your second favourite one ★★

Give only 1 star (★) to all challenges that you are okay to take part in it, in case your preferences are not available. If you give no star to a challenge, it means you are not interested at all.

36

Digital Literacy

Challenge giver: Institute of Interdisciplinary Research Team (University of Coimbra) Area: Peace and Democracy

How to strengthen the digital literacy of the population, with a view to identifying and combating false information that is often massively disseminated through social media, which is often used to influence (through lies) public opinion on a certain subject.

37

Food

Challenge-giver: Institute of Interdisciplinary Research Team (University of Coimbra) Area: Wellbeing and Happiness

New public policies or educational programmes to promote healthy eating habits and physical activity from an early age, while also considering effective measures to combat food waste, such as those conducted on a daily basis by the big food retail companies in Portugal.

38

Gender and Prices

Challenge-giver: Pâmela Aguiar, PhD Student and Gender@UC Project Manager

Area: Diversity and Inclusion

How to make citizens, retailers and policy makers aware of gender-based price discrimination. The best-known type of gender discrimination is the pay gap between women and men, but few people realise that not only do women earn less than men, on average, they also pay more for certain products and/or services. This discrimination is often perpetuated by governments that apply higher import taxes to women's products, making them more expensive. For example, certain personal hygiene products such as shampoo and waxing/shaving razors, but also services such as haircuts and laundry services that charge different prices for women's and men's clothes.

39

School failure

Challenge-giver: EqualSteam Project Team

Area: Diversity and Inclusion

Which role can the University and/or Governmental Organisations play in preventing school failure among basic level students living in socio-economically underprivileged conditions?

40

Isolation

Challenge-giver: Instituto Pedro Nunes, Coimbra

Area: Wellbeing and Happiness

How can digital technologies and innovation be agents for combating the isolation of rural populations, for example in terms of access to health care, medicines, therapies, among others,

apart from combating loneliness through classic social media and/or communication technologies?

41

Leadership

Challenge-giver: Ana Carvalho, Researcher (University of Coimbra) Area: Diversity and Inclusion

How can gender inequality in leadership positions be reduced in order to achieve greater parity in organisations in the Coimbra region?

7. Salamanca

Due to the University of Salamanca Rector elections on 7th of May, there was no on-site Makeathon event in Salamanca. This was unfortunately cancelled.

However, the central Makeathon coordinators still welcomed students and citizens from Salamanca to participate in the virtual European track. In this track participants were part of a European team and solved a challenge online.

8. Virtual European Challenges

Event location: Wherever you are, with laptop and internet connection. As collaboration platform, we will use Slack.

Contact person: Eleonore Roderfeld (eleonore.roderfeld@uni-jena.de)

Here, you find the virtual challenges. If you are not interested to participate online, just skip.

Later, we will match you with one challenge and around 3 other participants from across Europe. Together, based on your interest and complementing competences, you will tackle the challenge during the Makeathon event!

Please note:

- These specific challenges happen online. You can connect from home or any other place with a stable internet connection.
- You will need a laptop (with webcam and microphone) to connect with your team. Our main collaboration platform will be Slack, with chat and videocall. You will receive more information before the event.
- English will be the main language. You should have good English skills to communicate with your team.

Please give your preferences regarding the challenges.

Your favourite one ★★★

Your second favourite one ★★

Give only 1 star (★) to all challenges that you are okay to take part in it, in case your preferences are not available. If you give no star to a challenge, it means you are not interested at all.

42

Street art

Area: Peace and Democracy

Challenge-giver: EC2U Think Tank Team (from Poitiers, France)

How might we, as citizens, foster peace-building via positive messaging within communities? Focusing on street art as a means of expression, how can we together with local artists and citizens create an environment conducive to constructive dialogue and social change?

43

Gamification

Area: Peace and Democracy

Challenge-giver: ELEVA Digital Development Agency (from Pavia, Italy)

How might we leverage digital platforms and gamification to revolutionize civic education, making it more engaging and impactful for young people?

Specifically, how can we create a draft plan for creating interactive experiences (for instance a dedicated app, a platform, a role-playing game) that simulate democratic processes, facilitate understanding of peace and democracy principles, and encourage active participation in civic life? The goal is to empower users with a deeper understanding of their role in a democratic society and the importance of peace, thereby fostering a more informed, engaged, and active citizenship for the future.

44

Science communication

Area: Peace and Democracy

Challenge-giver: JenaVersum network (from Jena, Germany)

How can we make scientific knowledge more accessible and combat scientific scepticism, particularly in regions where prejudices or mistrust of research, scientific information, and scientists are common? Potential solutions could involve school projects focused on understanding how knowledge is created and teaching science in schools, as well as social media campaigns addressing climate change and its regional impacts.

45

European citizenship and EU elections

Area: Peace and Democracy

Challenge-giver: International Mobility unit - University of Pavia (from Pavia, Italy)

Over the years, political participation has evolved, especially among young people, very often taking new shapes: non-conventional forms of activism (such as engagement in the digital sphere, clicktivism¹, grassroots activities, and boycotts) have become commonplace.

Notwithstanding, there is still a long way to go in engaging a growing number of young European citizens in EU democratic life and making them aware of the importance of raising their voices, giving their say in the EU political direction and making their opinion heard on crucial current

common challenges (from climate change policies to foreign policy, from AI to migratory movements)

How might we increase European citizenship and a sense of belonging to the EU amongst EC2U student community? Which concrete actions, initiatives, and creative solutions could we design as an alliance to give our contribution to this crucial issue for the EU democratic and participative life?

46

Meeting places for people

Area: Diversity and Inclusion

Challenge-giver: City of Turku (from Turku, Finland)

How might we bring together people of different ages and backgrounds in a way that increases solidarity and inclusion? It might be digital or material solutions.

The aim of Kupittaa Partnership Project (Kupittaa Core) Point is to provide meeting places for people. Bringing together people of different ages and backgrounds is one of the key aspects of the project. We address, among other things, discrimination, loneliness, and social exclusion. Furthermore, we support encounters that enhance the vitality of the city and the emergence of innovations.

47

Mental health

Area: Wellbeing and Happiness

Challenge-giver: Info Jeunes Nouvelle Aquitaine (from Poitiers, France)

How can young people's mental health be better considered?

48

Physical activity

Area: Wellbeing and Happiness

Challenge-giver: Chaire Sport Santé (from Poitiers, France)

How can physical activity be incorporated into a general health promotion approach and be integrated into all living spaces?

49

Accessibility

Area: Diversity and Inclusion

Challenge-giver: Europe Direct Poitiers Vienne / Deux Sèvres | Info Jeunes Nouvelle Aquitaine (from Poitiers, France)

In the context of the European elections, how can access to voting polls be facilitated for Europeans with disabilities?

50

AI for sustainability

Area: Nature and Sustainability

Challenge-giver: Iberdrola S.A. (from Spain)

How can artificial intelligence contribute to the solutions that Iberdrola (a clean energy provider) currently offers its residential clients from a sustainability point of view?

Already available solutions: <https://www.iberdrola.es/en/services>

51

...

There might be a few more challenges posted to the online track in the future. If so, we might offer you the opportunity to change your preferences and to indicate your interest in them as well.

9. About yourself

52

Your full name *

Given name and family name, as it would appear on the certificate of participation.

[text field]

53

What applies to you? *

- I am a student.
- I am a university employee.
- I am a professional (non-university actor).
- I participate as citizen.

54

Your language skills *

This will help us to reduce language barriers.

- Confident to talk in both: English and local language
- Confident to talk only in the local language
- Confident to talk only in English

55

What would you like to bring in?

If you just bring time and curiosity, that will be perfectly fine as already.

A more specific answer here might help us to find you a matching team and perfect challenge.

Just some keywords on your expertise, your hobbies, skills, specific insights, interests, tools, secret superpowers, ...

[text field]

56

We would like to get to know you a little better. Please answer question A or B in just a few sentences.

- A) Are you already excited about first ideas or approaches to solve a challenge?
- B) What would make the Makeathon a success for you personally? *

[text field]

57

Here are some important points regarding the timing.

- To feel better prepared, optional workshops are offered in the weeks before the Makeathon. Topics: Ideation, prototyping, stakeholder engagement, etc. I will be invited via email.
- To participate in the Makeathon, I have marked 6 and 7 May in my calendar. I can be present for the Welcome and the Presentations (local and finale).
- For the teamwork, I can freely decide on how much time I want to invest. Nobody is expected to work 24 hours. I'm going to communicate my availability with my future team.

58

Consent to taking photos and videos

Staff from the University and EC2U will take nice pictures to document the event. There will be hybrid sessions to connect with the other universities via Zoom and a summarizing video will be available on Youtube.

I authorize the university and the EC2U Alliance to record images, audio, video, statements made during the "EC2U Makeathon" event, organized within the RI4C2 project, on 6-7 May 2024, with photographic and audiovisuals, to publish and disseminate them on the University website and related sites, official social networks, in print (e.g. magazines, books, brochures and promotional material of the University) and social networks and websites of the EC2U Alliance.

I also authorize the storage of the photos and videos themselves in the computer archives and I acknowledge that the purposes of these publications are merely of an educational / informative nature and refer to content acquired exclusively in the context of the activities envisaged by participating in the event. I can revoke my consent in the future. *

- Yes, I agree with appearing on pictures and videos.
- No, please remove me from public pictures and video recordings.

59

Open textbox: Is there anything else you would like us to know?

[text field]

60

Now, you may submit your answers.

By sending this form, you authorize the processing of personal data in compliance with the law 196/2003 "Code regarding the protection of personal data" and the GDPR 679/16 "European regulation on the protection of personal data". You can revoke your consent at any time with effect for the future. If so, please contact ec2u@unijena.de .

B. Annex B : Makeathon Handbook

I.	Makeathon	67
A.	Objective of a Makeathon.....	67
B.	Description of a Makeathon	67
C.	Expected Outcome	68
II.	Handbook to organize the event.....	70
A.	Overview of to-do's	70
B.	Organizing the team.....	70
C.	Create communication plan and steps	70
D.	Find active stakeholders	71
E.	Gather challenges.....	71
F.	Organizing the online part of the event.....	72
G.	Writing a manuscript.....	72
H.	Organizing the on-site part of the event	72
I.	Resources and Sponsoring.....	72
J.	Judging Criteria	72
K.	Intellectual Property Rights.....	73
L.	Pre-event	73
M.	The actual event	73
N.	Reporting and Documentation	73
O.	Timeline	75

I. Objectives of a Makeathon

A. Objective of a Makeathon

A Makeathon, derived from the words "make" and "marathon," is an engaging and interactive event that brings together participants to collaboratively develop creative solutions within a designated timeframe. The primary goal of a Makeathon is to highlight the innovative ability of both the European Alliance and the individual universities and cities involved, while also fostering the creation and implementation of sustainable ideas that contribute to a better future.

B. Description of a Makeathon

The EC2U/RI4C2 Makeathon combines creativity, sustainability, education, and networking to create an immersive and inclusive experience. The event welcomes students, cities, schools, and companies, encompassing a diverse range of skill sets and interests. The main event spans 24 hours and takes place at all EC2U cities simultaneously. It is accompanied by ideation workshops, networking sessions, and team-building events in the week leading up to it. Participants can choose to either form local on-site teams or join European virtual teams, enabling collaboration across borders. As a participant, there are two ways to get involved: If they already have an exciting idea or challenge, they can post it on the challenge board or pitch it during the networking event. Alternatively, participants can explore challenges on a challenge board, like ideas posted by other stakeholders, invite other people to join, and select one that aligns with their interests during the networking and team-building event.

During the Makeathon, participants will focus on solving challenges in four key sub-topics:

- I. "Diversity & Inclusion,"
- II. "Nature & Sustainability",
- III. "Wellbeing & Happiness," and
- IV. "Peace & Democracy."

These challenges will be curated prior to the event, e.g. from the discussions held during the 7th EC2U Forum in Poitiers.

In the Makeathon, various roles contribute to the success and collaboration among participants:

These roles include:

1. **Participants:** Students, citizens, schools (probably mostly students), employees who actively engage in the Makeathon. Ideally, four participants form a team. If seven or more people are interested in the same challenge they will split after 2h into two teams, following different solution directions.
2. **Challenge givers:** Organizations, companies, or individuals who propose specific challenges or problem statements for participants to address during the Makeathon. They define the scope, objectives, and requirements of the challenges, providing participants with a clear focus for their solution development.
3. **Organizers:** The team responsible for planning and executing the main line of events in the Makeathon (RI4C2 WP 5).
4. **Facilitators:** Guides who lead the participants through the Makeathon, providing support, clarifying guidelines, and encouraging a positive and productive environment (RI4C2 WP 5 + others tba).
5. **Mentors:** Experts or professionals with specialized knowledge who provide guidance, feedback, and advice to participants, helping them refine their ideas and navigate challenges (tba).
6. **Judges:** A panel of experts who assess and evaluate the solutions presented by teams, considering criteria such as creativity, feasibility, sustainability, and potential impact (tba).
7. **Sponsors:** if any/ can we have any at all?

C. Expected Outcome

A Makeathon benefits the EC2U stakeholders by providing a creative learning experience, fostering collaboration and intercultural connections. General benefits

- **Discover new perspectives and meet new people:** Through active teamwork during the Makeathon, you will come into contact with many individuals, fostering new connections and gaining fresh insights.
- **Learn new skills:** You will actively learn and experience a variety of useful methods for creativity and impact.
- **Enhance teamwork skills:** You will collaborate with new people from different fields, strengthening your ability to work effectively in teams.
- **Experience self-efficacy:** Witness how much you can achieve in a short time during the Makeathon, boosting your confidence in your own capabilities.

- **Expand career opportunities:** Participants will receive a certificate and badge, opening up new possibilities for their professional growth.
 - **Outreach efforts:** We actively promote our Makeathon through press and social media channels, acknowledging our event partners and the joint achievements along the way.
1. **Students (university and schools):** A Makeathon provides an engaging platform for students to participate in hands-on activities. The Makeathon encourages creative thinking and teamwork, allowing students to tackle meaningful tasks and work on innovative projects. It serves as a platform for students to learn new skills, exchange knowledge with like-minded peers from Europe, and gain exposure to cutting-edge ideas and technologies.
 2. **EC2U Community:** The Makeathon is an opportunity to address the EC2U Pan-European Knowledge Ecosystem. By bringing together stakeholders from different professional backgrounds, disciplines and universities, the Makeathon showcases the innovative capacity of the EC2U/RI4C2 community. This collaborative environment strengthens the local and European knowledge ecosystem, encouraging knowledge sharing and knowledge creation.
 3. **Universities:** The Makeathon provides universities with the opportunity to display their commitment to interdisciplinary collaboration, innovation, hands-on education, and creative problem-solving. In the Makeathon, experts and industry professionals will be involved, enabling universities to strengthen their partnerships with local companies and organizations.
 4. **Cities:** The Makeathon attracts talented individuals from different fields, providing an opportunity for the city to tap into the pool of diverse knowledge and skills. In the Makeathon local challenges can be addressed and thus contribute to the development of innovative solutions that benefit the community.
 5. **Companies:** The Makeathon offers companies the chance to become enablers of innovation by providing support, resources, and expertise to the participants. Companies can showcase their industry knowledge and establish themselves as experts in their respective fields. The event also serves as a platform for companies to connect with talented students, offering potential internships, bachelor's or master's thesis opportunities, and even potential job placements. Participating in the Makeathon can also enhance a company's image as an innovative and socially responsible organization.

II. Handbook to organize the event

A. Overview of to-do's

B. Organizing the team

The first task is to organise the team who takes responsibility to organise the event. There should be at least one member of each participating university:

- invites the other organisers to the organising meetings
- creates timetable (example from the year 2021)
- communication and marketing material that others may edit (example from the year 2021)
- modifies graphical elements of marketing, communications and event itself that all can use (also edited) (example from the year 2021)
- organise the technical platform (Zoom?)
- gathers the challenges submitted
- writes the manuscript draft (example from the year 2021)
- take responsibility of the online event broadcasting and directing (changes the picture from one university to another)

In the beginning of the planning one organising group is enough, but few weeks before the actual event there will be need to minor teams like technical team, communication team and marketing team in addition to the actual organising team.

The team must be gathered during the autumn 2023.

Makeathon cloud folder: <https://cloud.uni-jena.de/s/WtXAtMioa9D7wFL>

Makeathon pre-registration form for interested parties:
<https://forms.office.com/e/8zwGkNKhY5>

C. Create communication plan and steps

The organizers will create a communication plan for the event (see [example](#)) including pre, during and post event communications in traditional and social media as well as the direct communication with the stakeholders involved.

- To do
 - Create marketing materials
 - FB Banner

- IG Banners
- Twitter banners
- LinkedIn Banners
- Create OnePager for participants, mentors, sponsors etc.
- Make a guideline presentation (see template)

D. Find active stakeholders

In the Makeathon, there will be six (seven) different groups of stakeholders (s.a.). Here are tips on how to reach out to them:

1. Participants: Use social media, newsletters etc. Participants should be from different disciplines, genders, ages, and backgrounds. They can also be from different career stages (students at university or at school, younger researcher, university lecturer/teacher, older researcher or PhD student). If participants like to join a European team they have to be able to communicate in English.
2. Challenge givers: Use email and EC2U Events to approach challenge-providers to collect problem descriptions
3. Organizers: RI4C2 WP5 Board
4. Facilitators: each EC2U partner identifies facilitators
5. Mentors: Use EC2U Events to approach potential mentors
6. Judges: One judge shall be nominated per partner university.
7. (Sponsors: if any)

All stakeholders will be invited to use the registration platform.

- To do:
 - Set up registration platform
 - individual invitations for each group + guidelines (code of conduct), i.e. expectations + roles + responsibilities for participants, facilitators, mentors, judges
 - create general OnePager about event
 - pitches at relevant EC2U events (FORUM, VLS, CPC, what else?)

E. Gather challenges

A diverse range of challenges and ideas for Makeathon will be gathered by online as well as analogue methods. To submit challenges and ideas online a registration platform/survey will be installed where participants can submit their ideas. During the EC2U Forum in Poitiers the Makeathon will be part of the RI4C2 session where the audience can also fill out post-its and postcard-like leaflets.

F. Organizing the online part of the event

The organizing team will check the options of doing a livestream well in advance. Before the actual event the technical teams at each site must check that video and audio are working fine.

G. Writing a manuscript

The organizing team lead by Uni Jena will draft a manuscript draft that will clarify the procedure of the livestream sessions (opening, check in, finale).

In between: low-tech broadcasting at certain checkpoint times. EXAMPLE: that all teams should connect at 18:00 via zoom, there is a short hello. And then you say... "Let's see your entire team! And now all of you show what you are currently working on! How is it going so far, what are your challenges? (...two word posts) And don't forget to write your questions and requests on the board if we can help you."

More coming soon

H. Organizing the on-site part of the event

When organizing the on-site part of the event, establish a Makeathon Base Camp at a suitable location, like the university main building. It should provide a space for collaboration with tables, seating, materials (to be defined!), and some snacks. The Base Camps should also offer the possibility to project the livestream (a screen or a beamer) and make video recordings.

I. Resources and Sponsoring

Provide guidelines for managing resources, such as equipment, tools, and materials required during the Makeathon. Include information on how sponsors can contribute and guidelines for sponsor engagement

J. Judging Criteria

The organizing team will draft the criteria and evaluation process for judging the Makeathon projects including information on the judging panel, scoring system, and any specific categories or metrics to be considered. The draft will be presented to the MaCo for validation.

The teams will have to present one intro slide (template provided): Problem, Team. Background Info. 2) the first hands-on prototype (photo of action, poster draft, situation play, workshop outline) 3) the vision slide (how will it look like in the future).

K. Intellectual Property Rights

Clarify ownership and intellectual property rights related to the ideas and projects developed during the Makeathon. Outline any agreements or procedures in place to protect participants' intellectual property: *Idea Creative Commons CC BY 2.0.*

L. Pre-event

During the pre-event phase, which occurs 1-2 weeks prior to the Makeathon, participants engage in ideation workshops, team finding, and team building. This period sets the foundation for a successful Makeathon experience, encouraging creativity, diversity, and effective communication.

Before the actual event the organisers will

- GDPR
- Decorate the rooms. Provide some snacks.
- Prepare/Check the audio and video settings
- Assign one university to handle the countdown screen and inform participants when time is up.
- Arrange for attendees at the event location to have access to follow the online event.
- Ensure a last-minute promotion of the event on the day [before]

M. The actual event

The actual Makeathon is the main working phase where teams develop their solutions. It is a 24-hour hybrid event, allowing teams to work either on-site or virtually. The opening, check-in, and finale will be live-streamed to engage a wider audience. Seven (*one each?*) teams will pitch (*let's make it not thaat competitive*) their ideas at the end, following the guidelines provided beforehand (see Science Battle's judges guideline [here](#)).

N. Reporting and Documentation

The post-event tasks ensure a proper documentation and communication of the event's success], deliver gratitude to the stakeholders that contributed to the event. This helps maintain engagement, builds a positive reputation, and sets the stage for future Makeathons. Here are the steps involved:

1. Write an article: The organizing team prepares an article summarizing the Makeathon, highlighting key moments, achievements, and participant

experiences. This article can be shared on the EC2U website, social media channels, or in the newsletter.

2. Write the deliverable report: The organizing team led by the University of Jena writes the deliverable report. This report should document the outline and outcomes generated in the Makeathon.
3. Send Thank You notes: The organizing team sends thank you notes to the involved stakeholders, expressing appreciation for their efforts, dedication, and contributions during the Makeathon.
4. Optional (?) Create a compilation video (like the one from the [Jena Forum](#), 30 sec): The organizing team (or the university responsible for the online broadcasting?) compiles a video with highlights, and testimonials from the Makeathon. This compilation video should showcase the event's energy, accomplishments, and participant experiences. It is then shared on the university's social media channels and website, allowing a wider audience to see the impact of the Makeathon and generate interest for future events like the launch of the Pan-European Knowledge Ecosystem in Poitiers later in 2024.

O. Timeline

This report reflects only the author's view and does not reflect the opinions of the European Union or the European Commission. The Agency and the European Commission are not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.